

MAGNETIC GADOLINIUM-CHITOSAN COMPOSITE NANOPARTICLES CREATED BY RADIOLYTIC SYNTHESIS

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1 Introduction

Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) are a major class of nanoscale materials with the potential to revolutionize current clinical diagnostic and therapeutic techniques. The next generation of MNP-based magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast agents, carriers for drug delivery, including radiosensitizers in neutron capture therapy (NCT) [1], is incorporates novel nanocrystalline cores, coating materials, and functional ligands to improve the detection and specify delivery of these nanoparticles. Biomedical application requires the magnetic particles to be stable in water and in physiological solutions as well as to be coated with a biocompatible polymer [2]. Polymeric coatings provide a steric barrier to prevent nanoparticle agglomeration and avoid opsonization [3]. In addition, these coatings provide a means to tailor the surface properties of MNPs such as surface charge and chemical functionality. One of the most widely utilized and successful polymer coatings, in terms of in vivo applications, has been the polysaccharide dextran [4]. Poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG) has also been reported as a coating polymer for biomedical applications [5]. Chitosan is a linear polysaccharide composed of randomly distributed β -(1 \rightarrow 4)-linked D-glucosamine (deacetylated unit) and N-acetyl-D-glucosamine (acetylated unit). It dictates many advantageous properties, e.g. biocompatibility, biodegradability, bioactivity, non-toxicity, etc. The excellent bioadhesive properties of chitosan encouraged it used for Gd NCT via intratumor injection [6]. Chitosan has been reported as a biopolymer for the preparation of Gd-DTPA microparticle for NCP by using an emulsion-droplet coalescence technique [2].

It is important to note that nanoscale Gd particles are also interesting to develop because of size-

dependent modifications of structural and magnetic properties at nanoscale level [2]. Additionally, nanoscale materials contain higher effective surface areas, lower sedimentation rates, and higher stability than bulk one [7]. Radiolytic synthesis has been recognized as a promising method to produce metal nanoparticles in the present of stabilized polymers. This method has several advantages including reduced agglomeration due to immediate coating of the particles, absent reducing agents and less processing procedures in term of "one pot" synthesis. In relation of γ -irradiation and the synthesis of metallic nanoparticles, silver (Ag) nanoparticles containing chitosan [8] and poly (vinylpyrrolidone) (PVP) [9] have been reported. Photochemical reaction using UV-light and microwave have also been proposed for the preparation of gold (Au) nanoparticles [10, 11]. Li et al. [8] reported that using γ -irradiation to induce Ag and Au nanoparticles exhibited much smaller particle size and higher concentrated nanoparticles than the chemical reduction method. Although many designs and protocols in preparing Gd nanoparticles have been reported, to our knowledge, there has not been studied about the synthesis of chitosan-stabilized Gd nanoparticles by radiolysis methodology using γ -irradiation. Therefore, we study herein, the radiolytic synthesis of magnetic Gd nanoparticles in the present of stabilizing biopolymer, i.e. chitosan, using energetic γ -ray irradiation.

2 Experimental

2.1 Chemicals

Gadolinium chloride ($\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was purchased from Aldrich Company, USA. Chitosan with percent

degree of deacetylation (%DD) of 95 ($M_v = 7 \times 10^5$ Da) was provided from Seafresh Chitosan (Lab) Company Limited, Thailand. Acetic acid (CH_3COOH) was bought from Carlo Erbar reagent, USA. All chemicals were used without further purification.

2.2 Instruments and Equipment

Gamma ray irradiation was carried out in a ^{60}Co Gammacell 220 irradiator with a dose rate of $7.7 \text{ kGy}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ kindly provided by the Office of Atoms for Peace (OAP), Ministry of Science and Technology, Thailand. Ultraviolet and visible (UV-vis) absorption spectra were recorded over a wavelength from 200-600 nm by a Libra S32 spectrophotometer (Biochrom, UK). Transmission electron microscope (TEM) photographs were taken at an accelerating of 100.0 kV by a Hitachi H7650 zero (Hitachi High-Technology, Corporation, Japan).

2.3 Synthesis of Gd-Cs Composite Nanoparticles

Chitosan (Cs) flakes were dissolved in acetic acid to obtain a Cs solution (0.2% w/v). An aqueous solution of 10 mM $\text{GdCl}_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared. Cs solution with different concentrations (0.02, 0.05, and 0.1 %w/v) was mixed with different amounts of $\text{GdCl}_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.02, 0.04, 0.06, and 0.08 mmole). The mixtures were γ -ray irradiated with the doses of 1-30 kGy using ^{60}Co Gammacell 220 irradiator to obtain gadolinium-Cs composite nanoparticles (Gd-CsCNPs)

3 Results and Discussion

Radiolytic reduction generally involves radiolysis of aqueous solutions to produce the radiolytic species. For water radiolysis in the present of oxygen, the radiolytic species of e_{aq}^- , H_3O^+ , H^\bullet , H_2 , HO^\bullet , H_2O_2 are created as seen in Eq. (1). Here, the reactive species created by γ -rays induced both reactions, i.e. degradation of Cs due to chain scission (Eq. 2 and 3) [12] and reduction of Gd ions (Gd^{3+}) to form cluster of Gd particles (Gd^0) (Eq. 4 and 5).

3.1 Physical Appearance and Particle Formation of Gd-CsCNPs

All Gd ($\text{GdCl}_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) concentrations in the present of Cs solution of non-irradiation (0 kGy) is transparent without color (Fig. 1(a)-(d)).

Fig.1. Appearance of gadolinium solution with the concentration of (a) 0.02, (b) 0.04, (c) 0.06, and (d) 0.08 mmole in the present of 0.1% (w/v) chitosan solutions (in 1% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid solution), after γ -ray irradiation with various doses.

The γ -rays irradiated Cs solutions containing $\text{GdCl}_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ exhibited more intense yellow color than the non-irradiated sample. The color intensity increased with increasing the γ -ray dose. The intense yellow color was obviously seen when the samples were irradiated with the γ -ray doses of 10, 20, and 30 kGy. Since nanometer-sized metal clusters usually exhibit unique optical properties with their specific absorption and scattering [13], the formation of Gd-CsCNPs was investigated by UV-vis spectrophotometer. The UV-vis spectra (Fig 2(a)) of $\text{GdCl}_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ containing chitosan solution obviously reveals two peaks at 260 and 290 nm, which interpreted as the chemical structure changes of chitosan after γ -ray irradiation [9]. It have been explained that the absorption band appeared at 260 nm belonged to the C=O in COOH group and the one at 290 nm corresponded to a terminal carbonyl structure formed at C_1 and C_4 after main chain scission [9]. The γ -ray irradiated $\text{GdCl}_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ precursor in the chitosan solutions also showed little surface plasmon absorption bands around 413 and 473 nm (Fig. 2(b)), whereas the non-irradiated

samples presented no absorption band. This evidence confirms the formation of Gd-CsNPs in the $GdCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ containing chitosan solutions after γ -ray irradiation. The absorbance implied the particle size and the number of particles as well as the formation of Gd aggregates. The absorption bands were visibly seen when the γ -ray dose increased

Fig. 2. UV-vis absorption spectra of $GdCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ solutions (0.06 mmol) in the presence of 1% (w/v) chitosan solution (in 1% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid solution) after γ -ray irradiation with various doses.

from 5 kGy to 20 kGy. Increasing the γ -ray dose from 10 kGy to 20 kGy, did not increase the absorbance of resulted Gd-CsNPs, on the contrary, decreased. It was suspected that the particle size might increase and the Gd particle possibly aggregated when the γ -ray dose increased as high as 20 kGy. Fig. 3 clearly indicates the effect of the γ -ray doses and the Cs concentration on the

Fig. 3. Absorbance at maximum wavelength (413 nm) of gadolinium solution with different concentrations; (a) 0.02, (b) 0.04, (c) 0.06, and (d) 0.08 mmole in the presence of chitosan solution (in 1% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid solution) with different concentrations; (●) 0.02, (■) 0.05, and (▲) 0.1% (w/v).

absorbance. By increasing the γ -ray doses and Cs concentration, the absorbance increased for all given $\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentrations (Fig 3(a)-(d)). Considering the effect of chitosan concentration, the 0.1% (w/v) Cs brought the absorbance higher than that of the 0.02% (w/v) and 0.05% (w/v) Cs. It was evidently suggested that the polymeric chain of Cs stabilized and prevented the agglomeration of the Gd particles resulting in increasing the number of particles. It can be concluded that the γ -ray doses as well as the Cs concentrations affected the number of particles formed in the solutions. This speculation was confirmed by TEM (see section 3.2).

Fig. 4. Absorbance at maximum wavelength (413 nm) of gadolinium solution with different concentrations; (■) 0.02, (▒) 0.04, (▓) 0.06, and (■) 0.08 mmole, in the present of various chitosan concentrations, after γ -ray irradiation with the dose of 8 kGy.

The $\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentrations of 0.02-0.08 mmole in the same Cs solution (1% (w/v)) did not significantly affect the SPR band (Fig. 4). The SPR bands of γ -ray irradiated samples are identical for all $\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentrations.

3.2 Shape and Particle Size of Gd-CsCNPs

One of the key issues for the preparation of metallic nanoparticles is the particle feature and size as well as the size distribution. The particle shape and size of Gd-CsCNPs were observed by TEM. TEM images imply that most particles were formed as spherical shape. As described previously, the generated hydrate electrons (e_{aq}^-) and hydrogen radical, (H^\cdot), from water radiolysis are strong

reductants. They capable reduce metal ions (M_n^+) to lower valences and finally to metallic state (M_n^0) resulting in forming the metal nanoparticles [8].

Fig. 5. TEM images of Gd-CsCNPs synthesized from 0.06 mmole gadolinium in the present of 0.1%(w/v) chitosan solution (in 1%(v/v) acetic acid solution) after γ -ray irradiation with various doses; (a) 0 kGy, (b) 1 kGy, (c) 3 kGy, (d) 5 kGy, (e) 8 kGy, (f) 10 kGy, (g) 20 kGy, and (h) 30 kGy.

The large amount of reducing agents as a result of the high γ -ray dose induced very powerful reduction of $\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ precursor in the reaction system. To observe whether γ -ray irradiation dose affect the particle size as evidently seen in the absorbance results, the particle size was considered relatively to the γ -ray irradiation dose. TEM images as seen in Fig. 5 also imply that the particle size of Gd-CsCNPs is also affected by the γ -ray irradiation dose. In order to clarify the effect of γ -ray dose on the average particle size, the particles were randomly determined and plotted against the γ -ray doses. Fig. 6 obviously reveals that the particle size of Gd-CsCNPs was dependent on γ -ray dose. The present work found different result in the relationship between γ -ray dose and the particle size to that observed in the case of silver nanoparticles as

Fig. 6. Particle size of Gd-CsCNPs synthesized from 0.06 mmole gadolinium in the present of 0.1% (w/v) chitosan solution (in 1%(v/v) acetic acid solution) after γ -ray irradiation with various doses.

reported in the previous research [9]. It was found in the present work that increasing the γ -ray dose from 0 to 10 kGy, the average particle size of Gd-CsCNPs significantly reduced from 250 nm to 15 nm. The particle sizes of the Gd-CsCNPs from the irradiation dose of 8 and 10 kGy were identical and they have the particle size as small as 16 ± 2 and 15 ± 2 nm, respectively. The particle sizes observed from TEM image is consistent with the absorbance presented from UV-vis spectra. It is interesting to note that the particle size increased to 60 ± 10 nm and 78 ± 14 nm after increasing the γ -ray doses up to 20 and 30 kGy, respectively. This confirmed our speculation on the

decreasing of the absorbance as mentioned in Fig.3. One can be seen that γ -ray irradiation generated the Gd-CsCNPs with a narrow size distribution. Compared with irradiation doses of 5-30 kGy, the lower irradiation dose of 0, 1 and 3 kGy induced the larger particle size with the higher size distribution. Above results indicate that the γ -ray irradiation method is capable to synthesize and control the particle of chitosan stabilized-Gd nanoparticles in nanoscale range.

4 Conclusions

The magnetic gadolinium-chitosan composite nanoparticles (Gd-CsCNPs) were successfully prepared via one-pot radiolytic synthesis using γ -ray irradiation. The γ -ray dose and the concentration of $\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and Cs are the key parameters affecting the particle formation. The Gd-CsCNPs in spherical shape with the narrow particle size as small as 15 nm were achieved. The radiolytic synthesis would serve as a very mild, simple and effective way to synthesize and control nanoscale size of Gd-CsCNPs for further biomedical applications.

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